

feeding could be the major reason for the shift in virus transmission efficiency.

At Los Baños, RTV incidence in IR54, IR64, and some other cultivars having Gam Pai 30-12-15 in their parentage was very low before the 1986

wet season (WS) and very high from 1987 dry season (DS) onward. RTBV + RTSV incidence on IR54 and IR64 was very low in 1986, but very high in 1988 (see table). Gam Pai 30-12-15 also had high incidence of RTBV + RTSV in

1988. These results indicate the breakdown of IR54 and IR64 resistance to RTV in Los Baños in 1987 DS was due to a shift in GLH virulence. RTBV + RTSV incidence on IR36 was high in 1986, but low in 1988 (see table). □

Resistance to bacterial leaf streak (BLS) in hybrid rice and parental lines

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Five rice hybrids from IRRI and their male sterile (A) and restorer (R) lines were evaluated against two isolates of BLS in the greenhouse. Pregerminated seeds were grown in plastic trays, three rows in a tray, one for each F₁, A, and R lines.

Isolates 93 and 335 of *Xanthomonas campestris* pv. *oryzicola* were used to spray-inoculate the test plants at 21 and 30 d after sowing (DAS). The bacterial suspension was adjusted to 10⁹ cells/ml. Scoring was done 10 and 15 d after inoculation (DAI) using the *Standard evaluation system for rice* (SES), based on leaf area infection.

Reactions of different A and R lines and F₁ to BLS. IRRI, 1988.

Hybrid	Reaction ^a					
	Isolate 93			Isolate 335		
	A	R	F ₁	A	R	F ₁
IR46830A/IR50	7.2	4.9	7.7	2.5	2.2	3.8
	4.0	3.7	4.4	6.0	3.7	5.1
IR46830A/IR9761-19-1	8.0	8.9	8.5	5.2	6.1	4.9
	4.6	5.3	6.3	7.4	6.5	6.8
IR54752A/IR54	8.8	7.5	7.9	3.4	0.3	2.5
	3.8	2.4	3.2	5.0	3.7	5.7
IR54752A/IR19392-211-1	8.7	8.7	8.9	3.1	1.8	2.0
	3.1	4.8	4.3	5.2	6.0	6.3
Zhongshan 97A/Milyang 54	8.4		2.1	3.7		0.0
	6.2	0	2.0	7.5	0	2.7

^aScores are averages at 10 DAI on plants inoculated at 21 DAS (first row in each set), and 30 DAS (second row). 0-3 = resistant, 3.1-4.9 = moderately resistant, 5-9 = susceptible.

Of the five hybrids, Zhongshan 97A/ Milyang 54 was resistant to the two isolates in both inoculation stages (see table). IR46830A and IR54752A became moderately resistant when inoculated with isolate 93 at 30 DAS.

The two parental lines with moderate resistance produced rice hybrids with moderate resistance. The R line contributed resistance in F₁ for the A line-susceptible and R line-resistant combination. □

Sieve tube number in tungro (RTV)-infected rice plants

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To study the effect of RTV infection on phloem tissues, we collected leaves from healthy and RTV-infected rice plants. Cross sections of leaves of the same age were dipped in a saturated solution of phloroglucinol in 18% hydrochloric acid. The phloem cells per microscopic field were counted.

We found no necrosis of phloem cells in infected leaves. However, the mean number of sieve tubes was 123 in healthy leaves, compared to 73 in diseased leaves. We conclude that RTV reduced sieve tubes 41%. □

Simplification of sampling method for assessing bacterial blight (BB) severity

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This study attempted to simplify methods to assess BB (*Xanthomonas campestris* pv. *oryzae*) severity. Rice variety RD9 was transplanted into 5 × 5 m² plots at Pathum Thani Rice Research Center, Thailand, during DS 1987. Disease was induced by inoculation in several levels on border rows of seven treatments with two replications each.

Severity was assessed 5 times at 49 d after transplanting (DT), 55 DT, 62 DT, 69 DT, and 76 DT, on 8 hills per plot. Leaf area damage on each of the top three leaves of each tiller (LAD1, LAD2, and LAD3) as well as whole hill damage (VLAD) were visually assessed and expressed in percent. The average leaf area damage of leaves 1-3 (ALAD) and disease incidence for each leaf position (IL1, IL2, IL3, and ILT) were calculated.

At maximum tillering (49 DT) and booting (55 DT) severity on the third leaf (LAD3) was highly correlated with average severity on the whole hill (ALAD) (see table). At flowering (62 DT), close correlations between average severity on a hill and severity on second or third leaves (LAD2 and LAD3) were found. At milk (69 DT) and dough